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ABSTRACT

Erectile dysfunction (ED) is an important health problem in men associated with reduced quality of life. Implementation of phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors (PDE-5 Is) has revolutionized the management of patients with ED and PDE-5Is are currently considered first-line therapy of ED. This paper describes characteristics of the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics and possible clinical side effects of medications from the PDE-5 Is group. PDE-5Is discussed in the article include sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil, udenafil, avanafil, lodenafil, mirodenafil, youkenafil, SLx-2101 and simmerafil.

Keywords: phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors, erectile dysfunction, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, side effects.

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ФАРМАКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИНГИБИТОРОВ ФОСФОДИЭСТЕРАЗЫ 5 ТИПА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ЭРЕКТИЛЬНОЙ ДИСФУНКЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эректильная дисфункция (ЭД) представляет собой важную проблему мужского здоровья, приводящую к снижению качества жизни. Применение ингибиторов фосфодиэстеразы 5 типа (и ФДЭ-5) произвело революцию в лечении пациентов с ЭД. В настоящее время иФДЭ-5 считаются препаратами первой линии в лечении ЭД. В статье описаны параметры фармакокинетики, фармакодинамики, а также возможные побочные эффекты препаратов группы иФДЭ-5. иФДЭ-5, обсуждаемые в статье, включают силденафил, тадалафил, варденафил, уденафил, аванафил, лоденафил, мироденафил, йокенафил, SLx-2101 и

симмерафил.

Ключевые слова: ингибиторы фосфодиэстеразы 5 типа, эректильная дисфункция, фармакокинетика, фармакодинамика, побочные эффекты.

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FOSFODIESTERAZA 5-TURI INGIBITORLARINI EREKTIL DISFUNKSIYANI DAVOLASHDA QO'LLASHNING FARMAKOLOGIK VA KLINIK JIHATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Erektile disfunktsiya (ED) erkaklar salomatligiga ta'sir etuvchi muhim muammo bo'lib, hayot sifatining pasayishiga olib keladi. Fosfodiesteraza 5-turi ingibitorlarini (FDE-5 i) qo'llash EDga chalingan bemorlarni davolashda inqilobga sabab bo'ldi. Hozirgi vaqtda FDE-5 i EDni davolashda birinchi qatordagi preparatlar hisoblanadi. Maqolada FDE-5 i guruhidagi dori vositalarining farmakokinetika, farmakodinamika parametrlari, shuningdek, mumkin bo'lgan nojo'ya ta'sirlari aks ettirilgan. Maqolada muhokama qilingan FDE-5 i orasida sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil, udenafil, avanafil, lodenafil, mirodenafil, yokenafil, SLx-2101 va simmerafil o'rin olgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fosfodiesteraza 5-turi ingibitorlari, erektil disfunktsiya, farmakokinetika, farmakodinamika, nojo'ya ta'sirlar.

Introduction. Erectile dysfunction (ED) is a condition in which a man is unable to achieve and maintain an erection to a degree sufficient for successful intercourse. ED is a serious problem affecting both the psychosocial status of the man and his partner [1]. The incidence of this sexual disorder directly correlates with age: ED affects about 40% of men at age 40-50, at age 50-60 - almost half (48-57%), and in the older age group more than 70% of men are suffered from this problem. Bad habits play significant role in the development of ED, for example among smoking men it occurs 20% more often than among nonsmokers [2,3]. ED is associated with various comorbid conditions such as hypertension, hyperlipidemia, metabolic syndrome, lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) or benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), cardiovascular disease, psychological factors, diabetes mellitus, post-radical prostatectomy, antidepressant medication, and antihypertensive drugs, etc. [4].

Normally, penile erection occurs according to a certain scenario. In response to sexual stimulation, impulses from the cortex of the frontal and temporal lobes of the brain are transmitted to the amygdala (one of the most important centers of erection). Then the impulse is transmitted along the nerve pathways to the parasympathetic centers of the spinal cord, located at the level of S2-S4. With sexual stimulation, parasympathetic impulses begin to prevail sharply. It is accompanied by the release of the main mediator of erection - nitric oxide (NO) through parasympathetic non-cholinergic, non-adrenergic nerve endings [5,7].

Nitric oxide (NO), which is released by nerve endings and endothelium, activates the enzyme guanylate cyclase. Guanylate cyclase increases synthesis and intracellular concentration of the secondary messenger cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP). cGMP alters the activity of a number of specific protein kinases that are involved in protein phosphorylation and ion channel function. The action of protein kinases leads to the opening of potassium channels and hyperpolarization of smooth muscle cell membranes, accumulation of calcium in the endoplasmic reticulum and blocking the entry of calcium ions into cells due to the closure of calcium channels [6,8]. This leads to a decrease in the concentration of calcium in the cytoplasm, relaxation of smooth muscles and penile erection. The phosphodiesterase type 5 enzyme (PDE-5) breaks down cGMP, thereby providing penile smooth muscle contraction and detumescence. Today are known 11 subfamilies of PDE. They are subdivided into 21 subtypes. PDE isoenzymes play an important role in providing contractions of striated and smooth muscles, vascular tone, endocrine and other organ function [8]. Phosphodiesterases of other

types were found in the corpora cavernosa, but they do not play a significant role in penile erection (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Molecular pathways of penile smooth-muscle relaxation (by Lue T.F., 2000).

eNOS - endothelial nitric oxide synthase, cAMP - cyclic adenosine monophosphate, cGMP - cyclic guanosine monophosphate, 5'AMP - adenosine monophosphate, 5'GMP - guanosine monophosphate, GTP - guanosine triphosphate, PDE 2,3,4 – phosphodiesterases type 2,3,4, PDE 5 - phosphodiesterase type 5.

Blocking the PDE-5 enzyme increases concentration of cGMP and promotes erection [9, 10]. Therefore, drugs related to PDE-5 inhibitors (PDE-5Is) are the first line of treatment for ED [11,12]. The most common PDE-5Is currently include sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil, udenafil, and avanafil. Less known are lodenafil, myrodenafil, youkenafil (yonkenafil), SLx-2101 and simmerafil.

Methods: A literature review was performed in the PubMed, Science Direct, Scopus, Google scholar using the keywords; sexual health, erectile dysfunction, phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors, sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil, udenafil, avanafil, lodenafil, myrodenafil, youkenafil (yonkenafil), SLx-2101, simmerafil and side effects.

Results. Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters, possible side effects of PDE-5Is are shown in Tables 1,2,3.

Table 1. Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of PDE-5Is*.

Parameter	Sildenafil	Tadalafil	Vardenafil	Udenafil	Avanafil
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Tmax, h	0.8-1	2	0.9	0.8-1,3	0.5-0.75
T1/2, h	2.6-3.7	17.5	3.9	9.9-12.1	6-17
Protein binding, %	96	94	94	no data	99
Bioavailability, %	41	no data	15	no data	8-10
Effects of high fat meal intake	Mean delay in Tmax of 60 min Mean reduction in Cmax of 29%	Food intake had negligible effects on bioavailability	Mean delay in Tmax of 60 min Mean reduction in Cmax of 18-50 %	High fat meal intake does not affect pharmacokinetics	Mean delay in Tmax of 85 min Mean reduction in Cmax of 39 %
Duration of action	4 h	36 h	8-12 h	24 h	4-6 h

* Data are based on EMA (European Medicines Agency) recommendations on drug properties, with amendments and additions) [19].

Sildenafil (Viagra ®, Pfizer, USA). It is the first known PDE-5 inhibitor. Used in clinical practice since 1998, it has become the drug of choice for most men with ED. Sildenafil is used in doses of 25, 50 and 100 mg. Initially, it is recommended to prescribe sildenafil at a dose of 50 mg, then titration is possible. Fat meal slow down the absorption of sildenafil, reducing its effectiveness. For more than 20 years of use of Sildenafil, it has demonstrated high efficacy (up to 80%) and safety in various categories of patients with ED. Sildenafil, while minimally affecting libido, provides improved erectile function, orgasm, and general satisfaction with sexual activity [13]. Sildenafil is used “on demand” when maximum efficacy is required. Sildenafil therapy is considered to be quite safe for the vast majority of men taking this medication [14, 15, 16]. The side effects of taking this drug in most cases are mild and short-lived (Table 2). There is an orally dispersible film form of Sildenafil [17]. In a study by Damle et al. (2014), has been compared the pharmacokinetic parameters of sildenafil in a film form, soluble in the mouth and a standard tablet form. In both cases, the dosage of the drug was 50 mg. The pharmacokinetic profiles of both forms were comparable [18].

Sildenafil, along with vardenafil, has the lowest selectivity to PDE-11 among the PDE-5Is. This makes it safe when used in patients with diseases of the cardiovascular system, pituitary gland and gonads [19].

Table 2. Possible side effects of PDE-5Is*.

Side effects	Sildenafil	Tadalafil	Vardenafil	Udenafil	Avanafil
Headache	12.8	14.5	16	8.9	9.3
Rushes of blood	10.4	4.1	12	23.2	3.7
Dyspepsia	4.6	12.3	4	no data	seldom
Nasal congestion	1.1	4.3	10	7.1	1.9
Dizziness	1.2	2.3	2	no data	0.6
Visual disorders	1.9	0	<2	0	no
Redness of the eyes	0	0	0	7.1	0
Back pain	0	6.5	0	no data	<2
Myalgia	0	5.7	0	0	<2
Chest discomfort	0	0	0	5.4	0

* Data are based on EMA [19].

Table 3. Indicators of clinical efficacy of PDE-5 Is*.

Indicator	Sildenafil	Tadalafil	Vardenafil	Udenafil	Avanafil
Onset of action, min	25	30	25	30	15
Duration of action, h	5	36	5	24	4-6
Successful application rate, %	66 (50-100 mg)	75 (20 mg)	75 (20 mg)	70	65 (200 mg)
Dose range, mg	25-100	5-20	5-20	50-200	50-200

* Data are based on EMA [19].

Tadalafil (Cialis ®, Eli Lilly and Company, Great Britain). Tadalafil was approved by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) in 2003. It should be noted that the most important advantage of tadalafil is its long duration of action, reaching 36 hours. The drug is approved in doses of 10 and 20 mg, as well as a daily dose of 5 mg (FDA approved daily usage for tadalafil only). Tadalafil is well tolerated, but side effects such as headaches, dyspepsia, myalgia are possible (Table 2). Myalgia may occur due to cross-interactions with PDE-11 [20, 21]. Daily use of Tadalafil leads to a greater improvement in erectile function than taking it “on-demand”. For this reason, this type of PDE-5 inhibitor has also been produced in a 5 mg daily tablet form. Tadalafil has been used successfully for the treatment of ED in patients with BPH. In BPH tadalafil, administered once a day at a dose of 5 mg, has a double effect: it reliably reduces the severity of the lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) and improves erectile function [21, 22, 23, 24].

Vardenafil (Levitra ®, Bayer AG, Germany). Vardenafil went on sale in March 2003. It is used in dosages of 5, 10 and 20 mg. It is a fast acting PDE-5 inhibitor. Vardenafil is as effective as Sildenafil. The effect of vardenafil appears in 30 minutes after intake, but is weakened by high fat meal intake. Vardenafil is a highly selective PDE-5 inhibitor that has been shown to improve erectile function in a variety of ED men. Vardenafil has a rapid onset of action, is metabolized in the liver, and has a half-life of 4-6 hours. Clinical trials involving both men with ED alone and men with a combination of ED and diabetes mellitus, ED after prostatectomy have demonstrated effectiveness of vardenafil. Side effects associated with Vardenafil taking were observed in 22-61% of patients, moderate in intensity and dose-dependent [25]. There is a special dosage form of vardenafil (10 mg), which is an orally dispersible tablet (ODT). This form offers great convenience in comparison with a standard tablet, since the absorption of the active ingredient does not depend on food intake, and the bioavailability can exceed that of traditional tablets. The tablet does not need to be taken with water and dissolves in the mouth quickly (10-15 seconds) [26, 27].

Udenafil (Zydena®, Dong-A Pharmaceutical Co., Seoul, Korea). Udenafil - was discovered in South Korea and approved for clinical use in 2005. It is used in dosages of 100 and 200 mg. The drug can be used both “on demand” and daily, at lower dosages, which makes this PDE-5 inhibitor very convenient for men with different patterns of sexual activity. Udenafil can be used on a daily basis if taking tadalafil produces unwanted side effects [28, 29].

A phase III 12-week, multicenter, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study by Paick and etc. (2014) evaluated the efficacy and safety of udenafil at two doses (100 mg and 200 mg) in 167 Korean men aged 19 up to 70 years old with ED of organic, psychogenic or mixed etiology, lasting at least for 6 months. The most important performance criteria, along with some others, were changes in International Index of Erectile Function (IIEF) Questionnaire scores. Treatment with udenafil resulted in a dose-dependent increase of all efficacy criteria, with mild to moderate side effects, suggesting that udenafil may be successfully used in the treatment of ED of a wide range of etiology and severity [30,31]. High fat meal intake does not affect the absorption of udenafil, although it leads to a decrease in C_{max} by 20%. The pharmacokinetic profile of udenafil does not change with

alcohol intake. It should be noted that udenafil is not approved for use by either the EMA or the FDA [19, 29].

Avanafil (STENDRA™ SPEDRA™, Menarini Group, Germany). Received FDA approval in 2012. It is a highly selective PDE-5 inhibitor [32,33]. The recommended initial dose is 100 mg, it must be taken 15-30 minutes before sexual activity, and then the dose is titrated. The advantage of avanafil is that it starts acting very quickly compared to other PDE-5Is. Data on the number of attempts to have sexual intercourse within 15 minutes after administration show the success of the attempt in 64.67 and 71% of cases when taking 50, 100 and 200 mg, respectively [28, 32]. Side effects are minor (Table 2). Food intake may delay the onset of clinical effect, but avanafil can be used regardless of food intake [13, 34].

Lodenafil carbonate (Helleva®, Cristália Produtos Químico-farmacêuticos, Brazil). It is one of a new PDE-5Is. Designed and applied in Brazil. Lodenafil carbonate is a prodrug composed of two lodenafil molecules linked by a carbonate bridge. After taking lodenafil carbonate breaks down into monomers and the lodenafil molecule directly has a relaxing effect on the muscles of the corpora cavernosa. The peak plasma concentration and half-life of lodenafil are 1.2 and 2.4 hours, respectively. In 2009, Glina S. and etc conducted phase II clinical trials of Lodenafil, in which the effectiveness of dosages of 20, 40 and 80 mg was studied compared with placebo and it was found that lodenafil at a dose of 80 mg was well tolerated and significantly more effective than placebo. [35]. The same group of researchers completed phase III clinical trials in 2010 They compared 40 and 80 mg lodenafil and placebo. Lodenafil 80 mg was significantly superior to placebo and 40 mg. In general, the tolerance profile of lodenafil is similar to that of sildenafil and vardenafil, with adverse events including rhinitis, headache, flushing, dizziness, and visual disturbances. [36, 37].

Mirodenafil (Mvix®, SK Chemicals Life Science, Seoul, Korea). Mirodenafil, along with udenafil, is another PDE-5 inhibitor that was discovered in Korea. It was developed in 2007. The time to reach the peak plasma concentration is 1.25 hours, the half-life is 2.5 hours. The pharmacokinetic profile of mirodenafil is similar to that of sildenafil, with a more selective pharmacodynamic profile. Mirodenafil is 10 times more selective for PDE-5 than sildenafil, with less inhibitory effect on other types of PDE [38]. Today, there are clinical data confirming a similar efficacy for mirodenafil at a dosage of 50 and 100 mg [39]. There are also results of clinical studies confirming the mirodenafil efficacy in the LUTS and ED treatment when used simultaneously with alpha-blockers. Myrodenafil administration at 100 mg dose over an 8-week period in patients who were already taking an alpha-blocker showed improvement in sexual function and a decrease in the LUTS severity without significant episodes of hypotension [38,40]. Mirodenafil has not been approved by FDA.

Youkenafil (Yonkenafil) (Zhuhai Oxforston PharmTech Co. Ltd., Zhuhai, P.R. China). Youkenafil hydrochloride is a novel selective PDE-5 inhibitor for the treatment of ED. It is an analogue of sildenafil, but exhibits stronger inhibition on PDE-5 and milder gastrointestinal side effects than sildenafil [41]. Its safety, acceptability and pharmacokinetic parameters were evaluated in healthy Chinese male volunteers [42]. This study was also explored the effect of food on the youkenafil pharmacokinetics. The study was divided into 3 trials: a single ascending dose (25, 50, 100, 150, or 200 mg youkenafil), multiple dose (50, 100, or 150 mg youkenafil once daily for 7 consecutive days), and food effect (50 mg youkenafil single dose). It was obtained that overall tolerability of youkenafil was good. Youkenafil was rapidly absorbed after a single oral dose. Food intake impeded absorption efficiency but had no significant effect on area under the plasma concentration-time curve values. There was no apparent accumulation following consecutive administration for 7 days. Single-dose youkenafil up to 200 mg and multiple doses up to 150 mg were generally safe and well tolerated.

SLx-2101 (Surface Logic, Inc., USA) is a new PDE-5 inhibitor designed specifically for the treatment of ED. SLx-2101 is converted in an M1 metabolite, SLx-2081, which continues to be active. In preclinical studies, SLx-2101 demonstrated excellent potency at the molecular, cellular, *ex vivo* and *in vivo* levels, and pharmacokinetic studies revealed the drug to be long lasting, maintaining therapeutic levels for >24 hours in rats [43]. A randomized, double-blind, single-dose study in healthy male volunteers was conducted to assess preliminary safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics and

endothelial function [44]. Five different doses (5, 10, 20, 40 and 80 mg) were used, with six subjects receiving active doses and two receiving placebo at each dose level. Blood samples were obtained for up to 48 hours. Positive erectile response was registered at 0-6 hours post-administration without visual sexual stimulation (VSS) for 10-, 20-, 40- and 80-mg doses and at 24-24.5 hours post-administration with VSS for 20-, 40- and 80-mg doses. No clinically significant effects on heart rate, blood pressure or electrocardiogram were noted. SLx-2101 was well tolerated in single doses up to 40 mg with headache being the most common adverse event in active and placebo subjects, and visual effects were noted at 80 mg. The pharmacokinetic profile predicts inhibition of PDE-5 for at least 36-48 h at all doses tested allowing confident once daily dosing [44,45].

Simmerafil (TPN171H) (Shanghai Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Sciences, P.R. China) - is a selective PDE-5 inhibitor in development for the treatment of ED. To evaluate the efficacy and safety of TPN171H in men with ED, on *clinicaltrials.gov* platform was registered a multicenter, randomized, double blind, placebo-controlled, parallel design study. Study was started at 2021.12.31 and completed at 2023.02.14, but we could not find any available publications reflecting the results of this study. However, safety, acceptability and pharmacokinetics of Simmerafil for the treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) were evaluated in the study, conducted by Chinese investigators. The entire study was comprised of three parts: I (single ascending-dose study), II (food effect study), and III (multiple ascending-dose study). 63 healthy subjects were enrolled in the study. Compared with other PDE-5Is, TPN171H was found to have no impact on blood pressure and color discrimination. TPN171H was safe and generally tolerated in healthy subjects [46].

Discussion.

PDE-5Is have demonstrated high efficacy in randomized placebo-controlled trials, with limited side effects, and it resulted in their wide use in clinical practice. PDE-5Is are considered first-line therapy for the treatment of ED. Although most side effects of PDE-5Is are mild, these drugs also have been possibly associated with more serious issues such as visual disturbances, hearing loss, priapism and others. There are additional possible correlations with melanoma among others [47].

Side effects. Possible side effects of PDE-5Is are shown in the Table 2. The main reported side effects of PDE-5Is are headaches, dizziness, blushing, nasal congestion, dyspepsia, and visual changes. The most common visual side effects are photophobia, cyanopsia, and haze [48].

Due to the literature review by Mostafa T. et al., PDE-5Is have become abused among some men for recreational use to enhance their sexual performance. To counteract the possible side effects of such abuse, the media and health authorities should be aware of the potential adverse effects of such abuse and strengthen the regulatory activity to protect the customers from such risks [49].

Concern about this issue was been also shown by Wanjari M, Late S. (India) in their letter to the editor of PanAfrican Medical Journal. They tried to bring attention to a problem of the Sildenafil use as a popular recreational drug among young adults without a medical need. Sildenafil interaction with other medicines can cause serious life-threatening side effects. For example, interaction with nitrates, leading to a dangerous drop in blood pressure, can cause serious health problems, including heart attack and stroke. Sildenafil can also lead to longterm health problems. Some studies have shown that the drug can cause vision loss and hearing loss in a small number of users. The use of Sildenafil can also lead to psychological dependence. Young adults who use the drug recreationally may come to rely on it to achieve an erection. This can lead to further health problems and damage relationships [50].

On of the PDE-5Is serious side events is priapism (a painful condition in which an erection lasts for several hours or more). An analysis of the World Health Organization pharmacovigilance database obtained that PDE-5Is show significant signals correlating with priapism among a large international cohort (31,827 individual case safety reports). Authors notice, that further clinical study is needed to elucidate whether this is from proper or inappropriate use or other confounding conditions. Analysis also allows to make an assumption of possible relationship between PDE-5Is use and malignant melanoma, which warrants additional study to better understand causation [51].

Other treatment options for ED.

ED can be treated successfully with current treatment options, but it cannot be cured. The only exceptions are psychogenic ED, post-traumatic arteriogenic ED in young patients, and hormonal causes (hypogonadism). Most males with ED are not treated with cause-specific therapeutic options. This results in a tailored treatment strategy that depends on invasiveness, efficacy, safety and costs, as well as patient preference [52].

When patients with ED are failed to respond to PDE-5Is, following options might be applied:

Intraurethral alprostadil – intraurethral insertion of alprostadil-containing cream or medicated pellet;

Psychosocial intervention and therapy – sexual skills training, marital therapy, psychosexual education and Cognitive and Behavioural Therapy (CBT - group or couple format);

Hormonal treatment – testosterone therapy (intramuscular, transdermal or oral);

Vacuum erection devices – provide passive engorgement of the penis, together with a constrictor ring placed at the base of the penis to retain blood within the corpus cavernosum;

Intracavernous injections therapy – intracavernous administration of vasoactive drugs: alprostadil, papaverine, phentolamine, vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP).

Regeneration therapies:

Shockwave therapy – low-intensity shock wave therapy (LI-SWT) treatment for vasculogenic ED;

Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) – intracavernous injections of PRP (only in a clinical trial setting).

Other treatment methods:

Botulinum Neurotoxin A (BoNT-A) – intracavernous injections of Botulinum Neurotoxin A (large trials are needed to confirm the efficacy and safety of BoNT-A);

Herbal medicine and natural supplements – little available evidence of robust scientific data to support efficacy and safety of these drugs.

Surgical management of ED.

Surgery for post-traumatic arteriogenic ED – surgical penile revascularization;

Venous ligation surgery – is no longer recommended for veno-occlusive dysfunction because of poor long-term results;

Penile prostheses – surgical implantation of a penile prosthesis. The two currently available classes of penile implants include inflatable (two- and three-piece) and semi-rigid devices (malleable, mechanical and soft flexible) [52].

As first-line drugs in ED therapy, PDE-5Is has several limitations to use. Medications of this group cannot be taken together with nitrates due to the potentiation of the hypotensive effect of PDE-5Is. According to the recommendations of the American Heart Association, nitrates can be used no earlier than 24 hours after taking short-acting PDE-5Is and no earlier than 48 hours after taking tadalafil. When using PDE-5Is, possible risk of complications associated with sexual activity should be considered:

- within 3 months after myocardial infarction;
- with unstable angina pectoris or angina pectoris that occurs during intercourse;
- with heart failure of functional class II and higher developed during the last 6 months, uncontrolled heart rhythm disturbances, arterial hypotension (blood pressure below 90/50 mm Hg) or uncontrolled arterial hypertension,

- within 6 months after a stroke [2, 53].

The combination of PDE-5 inhibitors with other drugs is possible.

Conclusion. With all the variety of PDE-5Is, the choice of medication depends on the frequency of planned sexual intercourse and the patient's personal perception of the drug. Despite of their safety and tolerability in patients with ED, these drugs must be used only due to certain indications and with medical supervision. Recreational use of PDE-5Is, especially among young adults, is a dangerous trend, which may result in immediate and long-term health problems. Patients should be counselled about duration of action of a drug, possible side effects and principles of use.

Data on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of PDE-5Is should be replenished and always taken into account in the management of patients with ED.

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